

Screening and Identification of Bacteria from Crude Oil Contaminated Soil with Biosurfactant-Producing Potentials

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Abstract

Surface-active substances called biosurfactants lower interfacial and surface tension, and are usually generated at the microbial cell surface. Soils contaminated by hydrocarbons have been identified as a significant source of bacteria that produce biosurfactants. From crude oil contaminated soil undergoing bioremediation, bacteria that produce biosurfactants were isolated and identified through biochemical and molecular methods. The isolate ND 102 was identified as *Ralstonia insidiosa* BT48 with Accession number KJ848571.1 and 97% similarity. Isolate ND301 was identified as *Burkholderia anthina* with accession number JQ659867.1 and 97% similarity, while isolate ND112 was identified as *Klebsiella sp.*SR-143 with accession number KC455423.1 and 96% similarity. The methods used for biosurfactant screening included oil spreading technique, blood hemolysis and emulsification assays. The highest and lowest emulsification percentage was 50% and 20.8% by isolate ND 301 and ND 102 respectively. All isolates showed positive haemolytic activity and ability to reduce surface tension by oil spreading technique. The maximum inhibition zone of $19.0 \pm 0.1\text{mm}$ was by ND 301 while ND 102 with $4.3 \pm 0.3\text{mm}$ was lowest. The results show that these isolates may be useful for environmental bioremediation and clean-up of oil spilled sites.

Keywords: Biosurfactant, Emulsification, Bioremediation, Screening.

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Introduction

Substances exist that reduce the surface tension between two liquids, a liquid and a solid, or a gas and a liquid and they are known as surfactants. Surfactant of microbial origin are composed mainly of lipids, proteins, or carbohydrates, which are easily degraded in soil and water, they do not accumulate in ecosystem (environmentally friendly) unlike synthetic surfactants (Mulligan, 2005). Microorganisms produce substances termed biosurfactants, which have strong emulsifying and surface-active properties. Bacteria are the chief producers of biosurfactant though they are also produced by some fungi species (Desai

& Banat, 2007). Both water soluble and water immiscible compounds, such as glucose, sucrose, glycerol, or ethanol can be used by microorganisms to produce biosurfactants, which can either be excreted or stay affixed to the cell wall (Goulart et al., 2014). Biosurfactants consists of a polar and a non-polar moiety which confers on it the ability to accumulate between fluids phases thus reducing surface and interfacial tension (Mulligan, 2005). Biosurfactants have a wide range of application in Food, Agriculture, Cosmetics, Pharmaceutical and Oil and Gas industries due to their unique properties such as, specificity, low toxicity (biodegradable), pH tolerance and better foaming and wetting

agent. They can stabilize emulsions in a variety of industrial applications, lower the surface tension of various industrial and natural media, and break complicated lipids into smaller parts (Banat et al., 2010). Biosurfactants are classified based on their chemical structure and properties; Glycolipids are biosurfactants that contains carbohydrate moiety and a lipid tail, examples include rhamnolipids and sophorolipids. Phospholipids contains a phosphate group and a lipid tail; examples include phosphatidylcholine and phosphatidylethanolamine. Lipopeptides contains a lipid tail and a peptide head group, examples include surfactin and iturin while polymeric biosurfactant have a polymeric structure and are often composed of polysaccharides and proteins (Marchant & Banat, 2012). Surfactants of microbial origin have numerous advantages over their industrially produced counterparts, due to their low toxicity, high biodegradability and it remains active at extreme pH and salinity, hence the need for this current research.

Materials and Methods

Sample Collection

Soil sample containing petroleum hydrocarbon was collected from soil undergoing bioremediation (*ex-situ*) in Federal Institute of Industrial Research Oshodi, (FIIRO) in Oshodi Local Government Area, Lagos State. The soil samples were collected aseptically into sterile containers and refrigerated at 4 °C until use.

Isolation and Enumeration of Bacteria species.

Total heterotrophic bacterial count was determined in the petroleum hydrocarbon polluted soil using the spread plate method on Nutrient agar (Oxoid) plate as described by Chikere et al. (2009). One (1) gram of soil sample was weighed and aseptically transferred into the first test tube of 1 in 10 dilutions containing peptone water as diluent. The diluted factors, 10^{-3} , 10^{-5} and 10^{-7} (0.1 ml each) were inoculated on sterile Nutrient agar plate and incubated at 37 °C for 18 to 24 hours. After incubation, bacteria isolates were sub cultured based on colonial appearances on nutrient agar plate to obtain pure and discrete colonies. Gram staining was done and Gram-stained cells were viewed on X 100 objective lens.

Enumeration of Hydrocarbon Utilizing Bacteria (HUB).

This was done by vapour phase method as described by Afuwale and Modi (2012). Mineral Salt Agar (MSA) composed of $MgSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$ (0.42 g/l), KCL (0.29 g/l), KH_2PO_4 (0.85 g/l), NaCL (10.0 g/l), KNO_3 (1.5 g/l), Na_2HPO_4 (0.86 g/l) and bacteriological agar (20.0 g/l) was autoclaved at 121°C for 15 minutes and poured plates were dried at 50 °C. Whatman No 1 filter paper was cut aseptically to cover the lid of petri dishes. One (1) ml of diluted petroleum hydrocarbon polluted soil samples at dilution factor of 10^{-3} , 10^{-5} and 10^{-7} were introduced using pipette into petri dishes containing the mineral salt agar. The samples were evenly dispersed using sterile L-shaped glass rods. Whatman No 1 filter papers were impregnated with crude oil of Bonny light as source of carbon to the medium and placed on the lid of the petri dish covers. Incubation was done at room temperature (25 °C) for 5 to 7 days in an inverted position. The hydrocarbon utilizing bacteria with heterotrophic growth were sub cultured on nutrient agar medium to obtain pure cultures.

Screening of Bacterial Isolates for Biosurfactant Production

Blood Hemolysis

Hemolytic assay is commonly used in biosurfactant screening to determine biosurfactant-producing bacteria. The Blood hemolytic activity was carried out according to the method of Nordiyana et al. (2013). Bacteria cultures were streaked on blood agar plates and incubated at 37 °C for 48-72 hours. Greenish coloration (alpha hemolysis) and clear zones (beta hemolysis) around bacteria colonies will indicate lysis of red blood cells or positive hemolysis.

The Methylene-blue Plate Agar

Mineral Salt Agar (MSA) containing 0.2 mg/ml methylene blue and 0.5 mg/ml cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) and pH adjustment of 7.0 for optimal microbial growth was prepared according to the method of Meenakshisundaram et al. (2016) and thereafter sterilized by autoclaving. Plates were poured, dried at 55 °C and spot inoculation of each bacteria isolate was made at the center of the blue agar plate and incubated at 37 °C for 4 days. Positive biosurfactant production will be indicated by a dark blue zone of clearance around the colony.

Lipolytic Test

The lipolytic assay is used for screening biosurfactant-producing microorganism that act on fats and oils. The lipolytic agar medium composed of 1% tributyrin oil in nutrient agar was prepared according to the method of Sidkey et al. (2016). Spot inoculation of microbial cultures was done on the surface of the tributyrin agar plate and incubated at 37 °C for 48 hours. Lipolytic activity will be indicated by clear zones around the microbial colony.

Emulsification Index (E₂₄)

Mineral salt media was prepared according to the method of Ibrahim et al. (2013). Nutrient agar plates were inoculated with cultures of Hydrocarbon Utilizing Bacteria isolates (ND 102, ND 112, ND 301) with the highest screening activities. A loop full of each bacteria culture was transferred individually into conical flasks containing mineral medium and incubation by sub merged fermentation was done using the shaker incubator at 180 revolution per minute (rpm) at 37 °C for 5 days. Broth culture was centrifuged at 15,000 rpm for 15 minutes to obtain cell free supernatant. Emulsification index was determined according to the method of Balogun and Fagade (2010) with slight modification. Cell free supernatant (10 ml) was dispensed from each conical flask into test tubes using a measuring cylinder. Kerosene (10 ml) was added as hydrocarbon source into each test tube and the tubes were Vortex for 2 minutes and then allowed to stand at room temperature for 24 hours. Data obtained were imputed into the formular below to calculate the emulsification index (E₂₄);

Emulsification index (E₂₄) =

$$\left(\frac{\text{height of emulsification layer (cm)}}{\text{Total height of the liquid (cm)}} \right) \times 100$$

Oil Spreading Test

The oil spreading test is based on the ability of biosurfactant to reduce surface tension, causing the displacement of oil on water surface. The method of Ibrahim et al. (2012) was employed. Distilled water (5 ml) was dispensed into three (3) Petri dishes (60 mm x 15 mm) and 2 ml of crude oil was carefully

added to the water surface, forming a thin film. Cell free supernatant (1ml) of bacteria isolates (ND 102, ND 112, ND 301) was gently pipetted onto the focal point of the oil film in each of the Petri dishes. The spreading of the oil film, creating a clear zone on the water indicated biosurfactant activity. The zone diameter was measured in centimeters.

Biochemical Characterization of Biosurfactant

The biosurfactants produced by each bacterial isolate was characterized to determine the carbohydrate, protein and lipid content in the biosurfactant produced. Carbohydrate and lipid contents in the biosurfactant was determined using the method described by Van Handel and Day (1988). Lowry et al. (1951) was used to determine the protein content taking Bovine Serum Albumin (BSA) as the standard.

Biochemical and Molecular Characterization of Biosurfactant Producing Bacteria

Three (3) Bacterial Isolates with highest biosurfactant ability (ND 102, ND 112, ND 301) were identified by biochemical method using analytical profile index kit (API Kit) and apiweb identification software system. In molecular characterization, genomic DNA of the test isolates were extracted using Zymo research Quick DNA™ fungal/bacteria miniprep kit with slight modifications. The concentration and purity of the extracted DNA was determined using Nanodrop spectrophotometer 2000c (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA). The extracted DNA was further resolved on 1% agarose gel electrophoresis and DNA bands visualised using ethidium bromide staining. Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR) Amplification was done using 16Sr-RNA primer, and PCR amplicon sequencing was done according to the method of Joshi and Deshpande (2010).

Results

Morphology of Isolated Bacteria

The colony morphology of all isolated bacteria in terms of size, pigment and shapes with their Gram reaction is represented in Table 1. All isolates were Gram-positive and rod-shaped, except isolate ND 110 and ND 300 which showed Gram-negative reaction.

Table 1: Colonial Morphology and Microscopy of Heterotrophic Bacteria

S/N	Isolate Code	Colonial appearance	Microscopy
1.	ND 90	Mucoid and convex shape and entire with 10mm size in diameter	Gram-positive short rods in singles
2.	ND 91	Translucent and convex structure size equal to 8-10mm	Gram-positive long rods in singles
3.	ND 100	Milky and raised colonies, with an entire shape 5mm in size	Gram-positive long rods in chains
4.	ND 102	Pinkish colony with a convex structure size of 4mm	Gram-positive short rods in clusters
5.	ND 110	Mucoid, light yellow pigment size equal to 6mm	Gram-negative rods in singles
6.	ND 112	Mucoid, translucent, 10mm in size	Gram-positive rods in clusters
7.	ND 116	Milky and translucent column shape is oval and about 4mm in size	Gram-positive rods in chains
8.	ND 200	Mucoid and oval in shape, translucent size equal to 10mm	Gram-positive short rods in clusters and single
9.	ND 201	Convex shape with light yellow pigment shape equal to 2- 4mm	Gram-positive cocci in singles.
10.	ND 202	Convex shape with light yellow pigment shape equal to 2- 4mm	Gram-positive rods in clusters.
11.	ND 281	Mucoid and convex with an entire shape size equal to 12mm	Gram-positive rods in singles
12.	ND 300	Mucoid and milky with entire edge and size equal to 6mm	Gram-negative rods in singles
13.	ND 301	Mucoid with entire edge and size equal to 6mm	Gram-positive rods in chains and clusters.
14.	ND 310	Milky and translucent colonies in size 10mm	Gram-positive slender rods in singles

ND* indicates isolates obtained from soil sample containing petroleum hydrocarbon undergoing bioremediation in FIRO.

Screening of Hydrocarbon Utilizing Bacteria (HUB)

Blood hemolysis, methylene-blue assay and lipase test on hydrocarbon utilizing bacteria

(HUB) for biosurfactant production is shown in Table 2. All HUB showed varying degree of haemolytic activity with ND 301 having the highest value of 18.2 mm and ND 116 had the least value of 1.3 mm. All HUB isolates showed positive reaction in the methylene-blue and lipolysis assays.

Table 2: Screening of Hydrocarbon Utilizing Bacteria (HUB) for Biosurfactant Production

	Isolate Code	Blood Hemolysis (Zone of Clearance in millimeters)	Methylene-blue Plate Assay	Lipase Test
1.	ND 90	3.5	Positive	Positive
2.	ND 102	14.1	Positive	Positive
3.	ND 112	16.0	Positive	Positive
4.	ND 116	1.3	Positive	Positive
5.	ND 201	5.0	Positive	Positive
6.	ND 202	7.2	Positive	Positive
7.	ND 301	18.2	Positive	Positive
8.	ND 310	4.3	Positive	Positive

Screening using Emulsification Index and Oil Spreading Technique

Table 3 indicates the emulsification potential and biosurfactant production ability of the test isolates by oil spreading technique. In the

emulsification test, isolate ND 301 had the highest emulsification index of 50 % while isolate ND 102 had the least value of 20 %. In oil spreading test, all the three (3) test isolates (ND 102, ND 112, ND 301) showed positive biosurfactant activity.

Table 3: Screening of Biosurfactant Produced by Test Isolates

S/N	Isolate Code	Emulsification Index (E24)			Oil Spreading (Zone of Clearance)
		Emulsification Layer (cm)	Total Height (cm)	E₂₄ (%)	
1.	ND 102	1.4	7	20	4.3 ± 0.3mm
2.	ND 112	2.8	6.5	40	13.2 ± 0.2mm
3.	ND 301	3.5	7	50	19.0 ± 0.1mm

Carbohydrate, Protein and Lipid Content of Biosurfactants Produced

Table 4 shows the biosurfactant produced by the test isolates. ND 102 produced lipoprotein as indicated by 46.80 % protein and 39.50 % lipid moieties. ND 112 contained carbohydrate,

protein and lipid moieties with 34.23 %, 31.75 % and 22.95 % abundance, respectively, which is indicative of glycolipoprotein, while ND 301 produced a glycoprotein biosurfactant containing carbohydrate (38.75 %) and protein (37.90 %) moieties.

Table 4: Biochemical Characterization of Biosurfactant produced by Test Isolates

S/N	Parameter	ND 102	ND 112	ND 301
1.	Protein	46.80	31.75	37.90
2.	Moisture	6.05	11.07	6.50
3.	Ash	0.005	0.005	0.005
4.	Crude Fiber	0.0	0.0	0.0
5.	Fats	39.50	22.95	11.84
6.	Carbohydrate	7.6	34.23	38.75
7.	Energy Value	573.1	470.45	458.18
8.	Type of biosurfactant produced	Lipoprotein	Glycolipoprotein	Glycoprotein

Molecular Characterization of Test Isolates

The molecular characterization of the test isolates is shown in Table 5. The isolates were

identified as *Ralstonia insidiosa* BT48 (ND 102), *Klebsiella sp.*SR-143 (ND 112) and *Burkholderia anthina* (ND 301) with percentage similarities of 97 %, 96 % and 97 %, respectively.

Table 5: Molecular Identification of Test Isolates

S/N	Isolate Code	Identity	Accession Number	Percentage Similarity
1.	ND 102	<i>Ralstonia insidiosa</i> BT48	KJ848571.1	97 %
2.	ND 112	<i>Klebsiella sp.</i> SR-143	KC455423.1	96 %
3.	ND 301	<i>Burkholderia anthina</i>	JQ659867.1	97 %

Discussion

In this study, eight (8) out of fourteen bacterial species isolated were selected based on their growth in mineral salt agar media, and after screening them for Biosurfactant production potentials, three (3) bacteria isolates (ND 102, ND 112, ND 301) with the highest biosurfactant producing ability were used to characterize different biosurfactant produced. In hemolysis assay which is the preliminary screening for biosurfactant producing organisms, all HUB showed positive haemolytic activity. Selected isolates ND 102, ND 112 and ND 301 with the highest hemolytic activity showed β -hemolysis potentials. This result is in compliance with studies carried out by Akintokun et al. (2017) who reported isolation of microorganisms from pharmaceutical waste water, which were able

to hemolyzed blood and produce γ and β hemolysis respectively. Blue plate agar and lipase test for screening of biosurfactant producing bacteria, was positive for all the isolates, this result is similar to the work of Sidkey et al. (2016), who employed the same methods in the selection of bacteria species with best biosurfactant producing potentials. Anandaraj and Thivakara (2010) also reported similar result while working on crude oil polluted soil in India. In emulsification assay, the test isolates showed appreciable differences in their ability to produce biosurfactant with isolate ND 301 exhibiting the highest emulsification index of 50 % and the lowest emulsification index of 20 % was by isolate ND 102. Screening carried out employing the oil spreading technique was positive for all test

isolates which also agrees with the work of Balogun and Fagade (2010).

Biochemical characterization of biosurfactant produced by test isolates, showed that isolate ND 102 contained both protein (46.80 %) and lipid (39.50 %) moieties, consequently the biosurfactant produced by this isolate can be termed a lipoprotein. On the other hand, isolate ND 112 had carbohydrate (34.23 %), protein (31.75 %) and lipid (22.95 %) moieties indicating glycolipoprotein while isolate ND 301 possessed both Carbohydrate (38.75 %) and protein (37.90 %) moieties signifying a glycoprotein biosurfactant. Obelenwa et al. (2017) reported a similar trend where carbohydrate, protein and lipid contents of 49 %, 26 % and 11 % respectively were obtained from biosurfactant produced.

The preliminary identification done using morphological tests such as Gram Staining, revealed the selected organisms to be gram positive rods. Biochemical and molecular characterization of test isolates, identified the bacterial isolate ND 102 as *Ralstonia insidiosa* BT48 (Significant taxa % ID- 97), ND 112 as *Klebsiella sp.*SR-143 (Significant taxa % ID- 96) and ND 301 as *Burkholderia anthina* (Significant taxa % ID- 97) respectively.

Conclusion

From the results obtained in this study, three potent biosurfactant-producing strains (ND 102, ND 112, ND 301) exhibited maximum biosurfactant production and can thus be applied for industrial biosurfactant production and application purposes in Microbial Enhanced Oil Recovery (MEOR) and environmental bioremediation.

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